

THE EFFECT OF WORK TRAINING AND WORK ETHIC ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE THROUGH WORK MOTIVATION AT STATE VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL 1 STABAT

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of job training and work ethic on teacher performance with work motivation as a mediating variable at State Vocational High School (SMK) 1 Stabat. The background of the study departs from the importance of improving vocational teacher performance through strengthening training, work ethic, and work motivation. This study uses a quantitative approach with a population of all ASN at SMK Negeri 1 Stabat totaling 89 people (PNS and PPPK), all of whom are used as samples (population research). Data were collected through a Likert scale questionnaire and analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS) with SmartPLS. The results showed that job training had a positive but insignificant effect on teacher performance, but a positive and significant effect on work motivation. Work ethic had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance and work motivation. Work motivation also had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Indirectly, job training through work motivation did not have a significant effect on teacher performance, while work ethic through work motivation had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. The R^2 values of 0.811 for work motivation and 0.862 for teacher performance indicate that the model is able to explain a high proportion of the variance in both dependent variables. This finding confirms that work ethic and work motivation are key factors in improving teacher performance, while on-the-job training plays a greater role in boosting work motivation than directly influencing performance.

Keywords: *Job training, Work ethic, Work motivation, Teacher performance*

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of vocational education, including at the Vocational High School (SMK) level, is highly dependent on the performance of professional and highly motivated teachers. Job training is a key strategy for improving teacher competency. A study by Gutara et al. (2021) at SMK GP found that training significantly impacted teacher performance, and when combined with work motivation and professional competency, these variables collectively explained 70% of the variability in teacher performance ($R^2 = 0.700$). As theoretical support, Noe's (2017) training theory emphasizes that systematic training not only develops technical skills but also influences teachers' loyalty and effectiveness in carrying out their duties. This suggests that on-the-job training is not only an investment in technical skills but also in teachers' attitudes and motivation.

In addition to training, work ethic, which encompasses responsibility, discipline, and dedication, has also been shown to positively influence teacher performance. Risadiana et al. (year unspecified, but within the last five years) found that work ethic had a significant positive correlation with teacher performance in Denpasar City Public Senior High Schools, with an effective contribution of 4.71%. Similar findings were also reported by Dona Elvia Desi (2020) in elementary school teachers, where work ethic and work motivation simultaneously influenced teacher performance by 48.7%. On the other hand, work motivation serves as a psychological mechanism that enables teachers to internalize training outcomes and express their work ethic through optimal performance. A study by Dewi et al. (2023) at Bali Dewata Health Vocational School found that work motivation significantly and positively influenced teacher performance, along with experience and education. This reinforces the importance of work motivation as a key factor in driving teacher effectiveness.

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Another study by Nesha Maharani (SMK Negeri 8 Padang) showed that job training and work motivation had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. However, organizational commitment only mediated the effect of job motivation, not job training. This means that job training has a direct effect, while work motivation plays a role through a more complex pathway. Overall, recent empirical evidence suggests that on-the-job training and work ethic both enhance teacher performance, both directly and through work motivation as a mediating variable. These findings provide a strong basis for testing the research model in the context of SMK Negeri 1 Stabat, given the unique characteristics of the school environment, the North Sumatra region, and the specific needs of teachers and local industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teacher Performance

Understanding Teacher Performance

According to Janah et al. (2020), teacher performance is the results achieved by teachers in carrying out their assigned tasks, based on their skills, experience, dedication, and time management. Good performance is seen when teachers demonstrate loyalty and high commitment to teaching duties, developing teaching materials, discipline, creativity, collaboration with the school community, exemplary leadership for students, and responsibility in their duties.

Factors Affecting Teacher Performance

According to Janah et al (2020), factors that influence teacher performance include:

- 1) **Teacher Competence**
Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that teachers must possess in carrying out their profession. According to Law No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, there are four main teacher competencies.
- 2) **Work motivation**
Motivation is an internal (intrinsic) or external (extrinsic) drive that makes teachers enthusiastic in carrying out their duties.
- 3) **Work ethic**
Work ethic is the spirit, mental attitude, and values that encourage a person to work diligently, with discipline, and with full responsibility.
- 4) **Work environment**
The work environment includes the physical, social and psychological atmosphere at school:
 - Physical : adequate classrooms, learning facilities, IT facilities.
 - Social : harmonious relationships with fellow teachers, principals, and staff.
 - Psychological : a conducive work climate, support, and open communication.
- 5) **Training and Professional Development**
The work environment includes the physical, social and psychological atmosphere at school:
 - Physical: adequate classrooms, learning facilities, IT facilities.
 - Social: harmonious relationships with fellow teachers, principals, and staff.
 - Psychological: a conducive work climate, support, and open communication.

Teacher Performance Indicators

According to Janah et al. (2020), teacher performance indicators encompass several important aspects that demonstrate the quality of their professional performance. Based on this explanation, the following are the main indicators:

- 1) **High Loyalty and Commitment to Teaching Duties**
Teachers are expected to be consistent and highly dedicated in carrying out their teaching responsibilities.
- 2) **Mastery and Development of Study Materials**
Teachers not only master learning materials but also continue to develop their teaching materials so that they remain relevant and interesting.
- 3) **Discipline in Teaching**
The aspects of punctuality, compliance with rules, and consistency in carrying out the learning process are very important.
- 4) **Creativity in Teaching Implementation**
Teachers are required to find innovative and varied teaching approaches, not monotonous ones.
- 5) **Collaboration with the Entire School Community**
Collaboration with colleagues, parents, and the school is an important part of the performance indicators.

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- 6) Leadership that Becomes a Role Model for Students
The proactive attitude and inspiring leadership of teachers are role models and motivators for students.
- 7) Responsibility for Professional Duties
Teachers must have a high sense of responsibility towards their duties – both administrative and pedagogical.

Work motivation

Understanding Work Motivation

According to Robbins & Judge (2022), work motivation is a process that explains an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence in achieving a goal. Therefore, in the context of teacher motivation, it is the internal and external drive that drives a teacher to carry out their educational duties—whether teaching, educating, guiding, or carrying out other professional responsibilities—with enthusiasm, consistency, and a focus on achieving educational goals in the school.

Work Motivation Indicators

According to Robbins & Judge (2022), work motivation indicators consist of:

- 1) Intensity
How much effort does the teacher put into preparing and implementing learning?
- 2) Direction
To what extent do teachers' efforts focus on educational goals & the formation of students' character.
- 3) Perseverance
Teacher consistency in teaching despite facing limited facilities or diverse student conditions.

Work ethic

Understanding Work Ethic

According to Sutrisno (2020), work ethic is an attitude rooted in fundamental beliefs accompanied by total commitment to the chosen work paradigm. In the context of teachers, this definition emphasizes how teachers' attitudes, commitments, and professional values form the basis of their behavior at school.

Work Ethic Indicator

- 1) Discipline
Discipline is a key characteristic of a teacher's work ethic, demonstrated by adherence to school rules, punctuality in attendance, and consistency in implementing the teaching schedule. Disciplined teachers not only maintain regular learning but also serve as positive role models for their students.
- 2) Responsibility
Teachers with a strong work ethic demonstrate a sense of responsibility in carrying out their professional duties, from teaching and mentoring to assessing and completing administrative obligations effectively. This responsibility demonstrates the teacher's commitment to supporting the achievement of educational goals.
- 3) Hard Work
Hard work is reflected in a teacher's dedication to preparing materials, selecting appropriate learning methods, and seeking solutions to emerging challenges. Teachers with a strong work ethic will strive to ensure the learning process runs effectively.
- 4) Honesty and Integrity
Work ethic is also evident in honesty and integrity, both in assessing student achievement and in daily interactions at school. Teachers with integrity and honesty serve as moral role models for students and maintain trust within the educational environment.
- 5) Commitment and Dedication
Commitment is demonstrated through teachers' loyalty to their profession, while dedication is reflected in their dedication to carrying out their duties despite facing various limitations. Teachers with a strong commitment will remain enthusiastic about carrying out their roles to ensure student success.
- 6) Cooperation and Care
The teacher's ability to collaborate with colleagues, the principal, and parents, and demonstrate concern for student development, both academically and non-academically. Good collaboration supports the creation of a conducive learning environment.

Job Training

Definition of Job Training

According to Mangkunegara (2019), training is “a learning process organized to improve the technical, theoretical, conceptual, and moral skills of employees according to the needs of their work or position.” When applied to the context of teachers, teacher on-the-job training is a learning process systematically designed to improve technical skills (e.g., teaching skills, use of learning media), theoretical (understanding of curriculum and subject matter), conceptual (ability to design learning strategies), and moral (integrity, ethics, and professionalism of teachers). Thus, on-the-job training for teachers not only aims to increase teaching knowledge and skills, but also strengthen dedication and moral responsibility as professional educators .

Job Training Indicators

1) Technical Skills

On-the-job training for teachers serves to improve technical skills, namely the practical abilities needed to carry out the learning process. Teachers are required to master effective teaching methods and strategies, utilize learning media and technology such as multimedia or e-learning platforms, and develop learning materials that align with curriculum standards. These technical skills are crucial for teachers to create an engaging, interactive, and easily understood learning environment for students.

2) Theoretical Skills

Beyond technical aspects, training also helps teachers strengthen their theoretical understanding. This includes mastery of the applicable curriculum, in-depth study of teaching materials relevant to their field of study, and an understanding of relevant educational theories and learning psychology. With strong theoretical skills, teachers are able to deliver instruction that focuses not only on delivering material but also on considering students' characteristics, needs, and learning styles.

3) Conceptual Skills

The next indicator is conceptual skills, namely the teacher's ability to think holistically and strategically when designing and developing learning. Job training encourages teachers to design creative, innovative, and student-centered learning. Furthermore, teachers are required to be able to solve various classroom learning problems and develop long-term teaching programs that support improving the quality of education in schools.

4) Moral Skills (Ethics and Professionalism)

Teacher job training focuses not only on technical and academic aspects, but also on moral skills and professionalism. Teachers are expected to demonstrate discipline, responsibility, and integrity in carrying out their duties. Furthermore, teachers serve as role models in ethics and behavior, both inside and outside the classroom. A commitment to continuous professional development is a crucial component of these moral skills, enabling teachers to maintain the dignity of their profession while continuously improving the quality of education.

B. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

C. Research Hypothesis

H₁: Job training has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.

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- H₂: Job training has a positive and significant effect on work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
- H₃: Work ethics has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
- H₄: Work ethics has a positive and significant effect on work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
- H₅: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
- H₆: Job training has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance through work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
- H₇: Work ethics has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance through work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat .

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of research

The type of research used by the researcher is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2022), quantitative research can be defined as a method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a specific population or sample. Sampling techniques are generally random, data collection uses research instruments, and data analysis is quantitative/statistical in nature with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. This type of quantitative research was conducted to conduct research aimed at adjusting research and to analyze the influence of job training and work ethic on teacher performance through work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.

Research Location and Research Time

The research location was State Vocational High School 1 Stabat, located on Jl. KH Wahid Hasyim, Stabat District, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra. The research period was carried out for 3 months, from October to December 2025.

Population and Sample

According to Arikunto (2025) if the subject is less than 100, it is better to take all of them so that the research is a population study. In this study, the population is all ASN employees at Stabat 1 State Vocational High School, consisting of 68 Civil Servants (PNS) and 21 Government Employees with Contract Agreements (PPPK), so that the total population is 89 people. Because the population is less than 100 people, referring to Arikunto's opinion (2025), all populations are used as samples, which is also known as population research.

Research Data Sources

The data sources used in this study are primary data.

Data collection technique

Data were collected by distributing questionnaires to respondents using a Likert scale with primary data sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Outer Model Analysis using the *PLS Algorithm* , produces:

Validity Test

Table 1. Outer Loadings Values

	Job Training	Teacher Performance	Work Ethic	Work Motivation
X1.1	0.925			
X1.2	0.859			
X1.3	0.914			
X1.4	0.867			
X2.1			0.846	
X2.2			0.929	
X2.3			0.877	
X2.4			0.928	
X2.5			0.926	
X2.6			0.890	
Y.1		0.749		
Y.2		0.857		
Y.3		0.605		
Y.4		0.915		
Y.5		0.900		
Y.6		0.867		
Y.7		0.855		
Z.1				0.944
Z.2				0.887
Z.3				0.850

Source: Smart PLS Output, 2025

Based on the values in Table 1 above, the results of the outer model testing using loading factor/ outer loadings show that all indicators in each variable have loading values ≥ 0.60 . This indicates that each indicator measured is valid and robust. Therefore, it can be concluded that all items in the questionnaire have met the validity criteria, as can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 1. Outer Loading

In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1:

$$Z = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_1$$

$$Z = 0.315X_1 + 0.644Z + e_1$$

For substructure 2:

$$Y = \beta_2 X_1 + \beta_3 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.144 X_1 - 0.498X_2 + 0.340Z + e_2$$

Reliability Test

Table 2. Construct Reliability and Validity Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Job Training	0.914	0.915	0.939	0.795
Teacher Performance	0.920	0.934	0.937	0.684
Work Ethic	0.953	0.954	0.962	0.810
Work Motivation	0.875	0.889	0.923	0.800

Source: Smart PLS Output, 2025

Table 2 above shows that the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values for all constructs are above 0.70. This indicates that all indicators have high internal consistency and can be relied upon to measure their respective constructs. Therefore, the research instrument is deemed reliable and suitable for use in testing the structural model.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Evaluating a model with PLS begins by examining the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The table below shows the results of R-square estimation using SmartPLS.

Table 3. R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Work Motivation	0.811	0.807
Teacher Performance	0.862	0.858

Source: Smart PLS, 2025

In table 3 there is an R square value for both dependent variables for the work motivation variable there is an R square value of 0.811 meaning that the influence of job training and work ethic is 0.811 or 81.1% the rest is on other variables

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outside the model. The R square value of teacher performance is 0.862 meaning that job training, work ethic and work motivation are 0.862 or 86.2% the rest is on other variables outside the model.

Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Hypothesis Testing

Direct Influence Between Variables

The direct influence between variables can be seen in the *path coefficients* . The data processing results show the direct influence values, which can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. *Path Coefficients* (Direct Effect)

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Conclusion
Job Training -> Teacher Performance	0.144	1,536	0.125	Rejected
Job Training -> Work Motivation	0.315	3,111	0.002	Accepted
Work Ethics -> Teacher Performance	0.498	3,342	0.001	Accepted
Work Ethic -> Work Motivation	0.644	6,120	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation -> Teacher Performance	0.340	2,569	0.010	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS Output, 2025

In the results of Table 4, there are direct influence values as follows:

1. Job training has a positive but not significant effect on teacher performance with a t-statistic value of 1.536. below 1.96 and a significance of 0.125 above 0.05 means that job training does not have a real effect on teacher performance because the significance value is above 0.05 .
The results of this study are not in line with the results of previous studies, namely that training has a positive and significant effect on performance (Anwar, 2025; Ibrahim & Mesra, 2023).
2. Job training has a positive and significant effect on work motivation, with a t-statistic value of 3.111 above 1.96 and a significance value of 0.002 below 0.05. This means that job training has a significant effect on work motivation because the significance value is below 0.05. The results of this study are consistent with previous research, which found that job training has a positive and significant effect on work motivation (Putri et al., 2023).
3. Work ethic has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance with a t-statistic value of 3.342. above 1.96 and a significance of 0.001 below 0.05, meaning that work ethic has a significant effect on teacher performance because the significance value is below 0.05. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous studies, namely that work ethic has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance (Ferine & Handoko, 2025).
4. Work ethic has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with a t-statistic value of 6.120 above 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 below 0.05, meaning that work ethic has a real effect on work motivation because the significance value is above 0.05. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous studies, namely that work ethic has a positive and significant effect on work motivation (Novita et al ., 2023).
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance with a t-statistic value of 2.569 above 1.96 and a significance value of 0.010 below 0.05, meaning that work motivation has a real effect on performance because the significance value is below 0.05. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of previous studies, namely that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance (Tarigan & Anwar , 2024).

Indirect Influence Between Variables

The indirect influence between variables can be seen in the *specific indirect effects values* . The data processing results show the indirect effect values, which can be seen in Table 5 below.

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Table 5. *Specific Indirect Effects*

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Conclusion
Job Training -> Work Motivation -> Teacher Performance	0.107	1,901	0.058	Rejected
Work Ethics -> Work Motivation -> Teacher Performance	0.219	2,503	0.013	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS, 2025

In table 5 there is an indirect influence between variables which will be explained as follows:

1. Job training has a positive and significant effect on performance through work motivation with a t-statistic value of 1.901. A significance value of 0.058 is below 1.96, and a significance value of 0.058 is above 0.05, indicating that work motivation plays a less significant role as an intervening variable between job training and teacher performance. The results of this study also align with previous research (Neza & Rivai, 2020).
2. Work ethic has a positive and significant effect on performance through work motivation, with a t-statistic value of 2.503 above 1.96 and a significance value of 0.013 below 0.05. This indicates that work motivation acts as an intervening variable between transformational leadership and performance. The results of this study also align with previous research (Lamere et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

1. Job training has a positive but not significant effect on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
2. Job training has a positive and significant effect on work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
3. Work ethic has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
4. Work ethic has a positive and significant influence on work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
6. Job training has a positive but insignificant effect on teacher performance through work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.
7. Work ethic has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance through work motivation at State Vocational High School 1 Stabat.

SUGGESTION

1. The teacher with the lowest score stated, "I arrive at class on time according to the teaching schedule." Therefore, the suggestion is to make punctuality a primary indicator in teacher performance assessments, and support it with a class attendance system directly supervised by the curriculum representative. This will encourage teachers to be more disciplined because there are clear consequences and rewards.
2. The lowest-scoring work motivation statement was "I continue to carry out my teaching duties despite facing various difficulties." In this case, SMK Negeri 1 Stabat needs to build a mentoring and support program for teachers (e.g., mentoring, a forum for sharing difficulties, and access to counseling), so that when teachers face various obstacles, they still feel supported and motivated to carry out their teaching duties well.
3. The work ethic with the lowest score statement is "I have a high commitment to teaching and student development duties." SMK Negeri 1 Stabat needs to provide awards and professional development opportunities (such as training, workshops, or strategic job promotions) for teachers who demonstrate a high commitment to teaching and student development, so that this commitment is maintained and becomes an example for other teachers.
4. The job training with the lowest score was "The training provided an understanding of learning theories relevant to my duties as a teacher." SMK Negeri 1 Stabat needs to design and select a training program that is truly based on teacher needs (need assessment) and their teaching field, then complete it with practical sessions and follow-up assignments in class, so that the learning theories provided feel relevant and can be directly applied in teaching.

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